

Curation progress of Chang'E-5 Lunar Samples in France: Preliminary Results from Gas, Magnetic, and Grain Extraction. T. Jiang¹, J. Duprat¹, L. Amand¹, M. Morand¹, Y. Garino¹, S. Boccato¹, J.-C. Viennet¹, F. Poulet^{2,3}, C. Pilorget^{2,10}, R. Brunetto², D. Loizeau², G. Avicé³, F. Moynier³, F. Vayrac³, C. Engrand⁴, L. Delauche⁴, J. Gattacceca⁵, C. Maurel⁵, P. Rochette⁵, S. Kassi⁶, H. Fleurbayac⁶, B. Sabot⁷, I. de L. Chacartegui Rojo^{3,7}, F. Girault³, P.-Y. Meslin⁸, F. Rocard⁹, C. Mustin⁹. ¹Sorbonne Université/MNHN/CNRS UMR 7590, IMPMC, 75005 Paris, France ²IAS, Université Paris-Saclay, CNRS, Orsay, France ³Université Paris Cité, IPGP, CNRS, F-75005, Paris, France ⁴IJCLab, Université Paris-Saclay, CNRS/IN2P3, Orsay 91405, France ⁵CEREGE, CNRS, Aix Marseille Université, IRD, INRAE, Aix-en-Provence 13545, France ⁶LIPhy, Univ. Grenoble Alpes, CNRS, 38000 Grenoble, France ⁷Université Paris-Saclay, CEA, LIST, LNE-LNHB, Palaiseau, 91120, France. ⁸IRAP, Université de Toulouse/CNRS/CNES, Toulouse, 31400 France. ⁹CNES, Paris, France. ¹⁰Institut Universitaire de France, Paris, France.

Introduction: China's Chang'E-5 (CE-5) mission successfully returned ~1.73 kg of lunar samples from the northeastern region of Oceanus Procellarum in 2020 [1,2]. The landing site, located among the Moon's youngest mare basalts [3-6], lies at a higher latitude than those explored by NASA's Apollo and the USSR's Luna missions, offering a unique opportunity to study previously unexamined lunar materials.

Samples of 1.0 g of surface-scooped (CE5C0100) and 0.5 g of drilled material (CE5Z0800) were offered to France as a state gift. Upon arrival in France, the two samples (here after CE5-FR) were stored at the Muséum national d'Histoire naturelle (MNHN) in Paris under ultra-pure nitrogen (<1 ppm O₂ and H₂O). A curation program was initiated to conduct non-invasive and non-destructive preliminary characterization of the samples and provide reference data before their allocation to the French scientific community through calls under the supervision of CNES.

The CE5-FR samples were delivered in glass vials stored within two aluminium containers. We performed X-ray Computed Tomography (XCT) to obtain images of containers components and volumes including the inner Teflon vial support. The XCT scans at a spatial resolution of 60 µm/voxel allowed to identify several tens large grains (> 500 µm) together with grains with higher density, heterogeneity, or void space (probably agglutinate). Here, we present preliminary results on the opening of the containers and first sample analysis.

Methods: A dedicated gas extraction apparatus (Fig. 1) was developed by the Cellule Project instrumentation group at IMPMC in close collaboration with IPGP, to recover the container's gas by piercing the containers under vacuum. The overall apparatus was designed to operate on the CE5-FR container in the dedicated glovebox under ultra-pure nitrogen atmosphere.

The drilled sample container opening operation was conducted 3rd February 2026. The container's base was punctured, and the gas was transferred into bottles that had previously been emptied and cleaned under ultra-high vacuum. The collected gas was analysed with a custom-built infrared optical spectrometer at LIPhy for H₂O, CO₂, CO, and CH₄ concentration. Argon concentration and isotopic composition were measured with a Noblesse HR 3F6M mass spectrometer at IPGP.

Non-invasive measurements, including mass and magnetic susceptibility, were conducted inside the glovebox on the bulk sample without opening the vials. The sample mass was measured using a Sartorius TE64 balance with 0.1 mg precision. A SM150L instrument by ZH instrument was used for the magnetic susceptibility measurement in a magnetic field of 80 A/m and a variable frequency from 63 Hz to 16 kHz. A magnetic standard material was used for repeated calibration, and the signal of the empty sample holder was subtracted to the measurements.

The sample vial was transferred into a stainless-steel cylinder for storage. An optical sensor on the glass window allows monitoring of O₂ levels inside the cylinder without opening it. We performed tests to ensure that the cylinder can keep the O₂ level in a few ppm levels for several months.

On the opening of the containers, we noticed the presence of a small amount of sample on the surface of the vials Teflon support. These grains probably escaped from the vial during the gas extraction process. The Teflon support was closed back into the aluminium container, taken out of the glovebox, and then transported to the ISO7 MYRTHO clean room at IJCLab in Orsay. The surface of the Teflon support was scanned using a Keyence VHX 7000 microscope. We extracted the largest grains (50 – 300 µm) into a quartz dish using a dry brush under binocular. The extracted grains were further documented with the Keyence microscope in high resolution mode.

Fig. 1. Image of the container designed for gas extraction inside the glovebox.

Results:

Gas analysis. ~640 ppm CO₂, ~9.6 ppm CO, ~2 ppm CH₄, and ~13.91% of O₂ were detected by IR spectroscopy in the gas extracted from the aluminium container. The H₂O level is about 1.4 ppm. Noble gas analysis of the extracted gas detected a large quantity of argon (7940 ppm, i.e. 85% of the expected amount if extracted gas was pure air) with a ⁴⁰Ar/³⁶Ar isotopic ratio of ~300 (identical to the one of atmospheric Ar). These measurements indicate that the gas contained in the containers was compatible with terrestrial

atmosphere. The low level of H₂O may be due to trapping of water on the ultra-clean bottles' inner surfaces or on the sample itself. One of the bottles was heated to 70 °C to release the water trapped on the inner surface, and then the gas was flushed to the spectrometer tube, where the measured H₂O value was about 40 ppm, which is still very dry. It is thus possible that the sample trapped a substantial part of the water present in the gas initially present in the container.

Mass and Magnetic analysis. The mass of the sample with the vial (and lid) is 15.8798 g. Magnetic susceptibility of the drilled sample at 16 kHz is $\chi = 1.11 \times 10^{-5} \text{ m}^3 \text{ kg}^{-1}$ assuming a lunar sample mass of 500 mg, indicating a metal content of 2.1 wt.%. This value increased by 24% as the frequency decreased from 16 kHz to 63 Hz. This frequency dependence of the magnetic susceptibility indicates that most if not all magnetic minerals are in a superparamagnetic state. This is interpreted as the presence of abundant nanophase iron (*npFe*) in the sample.

Grain extraction. We extracted ~150 grains that had escaped from the vial and were present on the surface of the Teflon holder of the drilled sample vial. Their sizes range from ~50 to 300 μm , and the particles exhibit a large variety of color, transparency (opaque vs. transparent), and morphology (smooth crystal, rough surface, inclusions, or spherical glass bead, etc.) (Fig. 2).

Fig. 2. Optical images of individual grains extracted from the CE5-FR drilled sample, taken with the Keyence VHX700 microscope. The scale (f) is the same for all subfigures.

Future directions: All the extracted grains will be documented (dimensions, color, shape, etc.). Then they will be further characterized by FTIR, XRD, and possibly Raman spectra to provide the basic composition information. Smaller grains (<50 μm) will be further extracted using a micro-manipulator installed in the dedicated clean room at IPGP.

The opening of the container with the scooped sample is scheduled for March 2026. The same analysis protocol (gas, mass, and magnetic susceptibility) will be carried out immediately after the opening, enabling the direct comparison of the two samples.

A small fraction powder of samples (5-10% in mass), both for the scooped and drilled samples, and large grains with size >500 μm will be extracted and placed on a dedicated sapphire dish (10 and 15 mm diameter) and sealed in faculty-to-faculty-transfer-container (FFTC) similar to those used for Hayabusa2 samples [7, 8].

By the time of the conference, microanalysis of the extracted powder and large grains will be conducted at the Institut d'Astrophysique Spatiale (IAS) using the

hyperspectral microscope MicrOmega (near-infrared: 0.99–3.65 μm , ~20 $\mu\text{m}/\text{pixel}$, [9, 10]) installed on PTAL setup and FTIR I2SES facilities microscopy (mid-infrared: 2.5–12.5 μm (4,000–800 cm^{-1}), 5 $\mu\text{m}/\text{pixel}$). Both imaging spectrometers are installed in a dedicated custom-made glovebox flushed with ultra-pure N₂. The gas purity inside the gloveboxes will be constantly monitored using dedicated O₂/H₂O sensors. Both instruments will support the identification of key mineral phases (e.g., olivine, pyroxene, plagioclase) in the samples and an assessment of the OH/H₂O signatures will be performed.

High-resolution XRD will be conducted at IMPMC. Analysis at micron or sub-micron scale of large grains will be performed using XCT at the French synchrotron facility SOLEIL.

Non-invasive gamma-ray spectrometry and radon emanation analyses of the powder will be performed at Laboratoire National Henri Becquerel (CEA/LNHB), the national laboratory responsible for the development of primary standards for nuclear metrology in France [11]. These analyses will help interpreting radon measurements made by Chang'e-6/DORN [12].

These analyses will provide a comprehensive dataset documenting the mass, morphology, and mineralogy of both individual grains and bulk-powder batches. The results will be compiled into a catalogue database and made available through a dedicated website under CNES supervision. Further details will be presented at the conference.

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